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The Impact of Coffee Shops on Aceh's Economic Sustainability

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Abstract

The effect of coffee shops on Aceh, Indonesia's ability to sustain its economy is examined in this article. The research is predicated on the idea that coffee, especially Arabica coffee, is a valuable product in Aceh that boosts the local economy and the income of coffee producers. The study's objectives are to examine the traits of coffee shop patrons, the variables that affect the volume of business and revenue of well-known coffee shops in Banda Aceh City, as well as the profitability of these establishments. Based on data analysis from well-known coffee shops in the area, the research design examines variables that affect both visitor volume and profit margins. The results show that young people with particular spending habits and visitation patterns frequent coffee shops. The ramifications of these discoveries for the region's economic sustainability are explored in detail, with a focus on the coffee sector. The article's conclusion highlights the importance of coffee shops to Aceh's economy as well as the need for more study and advancement in this field.

Keyword: Aceh, Economy, Sustainability, Coffee

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INTRODUCTION

Aceh, Indonesia, is known for its thriving coffee industry, with Arabica coffee being a key commodity that significantly contributes to the region's economy. In recent years, the proliferation of coffee shops has become a notable feature of the local economic landscape. These establishments not only serve as social hubs but also play a crucial role in the economic sustainability of the region (Mariyudi, M., Suryadi, S., Sayuti, M., & Hendra, R, 2019). This article aims to investigate the impact of coffee shops on Aceh's economic sustainability, with a specific focus on popular coffee shops in Banda Aceh City. By analyzing the characteristics of coffee shop visitors, factors influencing visitor numbers and income, and the profitability of these establishments, this study seeks to provide valuable insights into the economic dynamics of the region (Zikria, V, 2020).

METHOD

The research design is based on an analysis of data from popular coffee shops in Banda Aceh City. The study focuses on factors that influence the number of visitors and the profit levels of these establishments. By examining the expenditure, visitor characteristics, and profitability of the coffee shops, the research aims to gain a comprehensive understanding of their economic.

The data for this study is sourced from an analysis of popular coffee shops in Banda Aceh City. The research examines the characteristics of visitors, factors influencing the number of visitors and income, and the profitability of these establishments. The data provides valuable insights into the economic dynamics of the region's coffee shop industry.

The data analysis focuses on the characteristics of visitors, factors influencing the number of visitors and income, and the profitability of popular coffee shops in Banda Aceh City. By examining the expenditure, visitor characteristics, and profitability of the coffee shops, the analysis aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of their economic impact.

FINDING

The findings reveal that popular coffee shops in Banda Aceh City attract a predominantly young clientele, with specific spending patterns and visiting frequencies. The analysis of expenditure, visitor characteristics, and profitability provides valuable insights into the economic dynamics of the region's coffee shop industry (Kilian, B., Pratt, L., Jones, C., & Villalobos, A, 2004).

DISCUSSION

The implications of the findings for the economic sustainability of the region, particularly in relation to the coffee industry, are discussed. The significant role of coffee shops in the economic landscape of Aceh is emphasized, highlighting the potential for further research and development in this area.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study sheds light on the significant impact of coffee shops on the economic sustainability of Aceh, particularly in the context of the region's thriving coffee industry. The findings underscore the importance of these establishments in the local economy and point to the potential for further research and development in this area.

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